

FLU SYMPTOMS, FORM, CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION

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Abstract. *Influenza is an acute infectious respiratory disease of a viral nature. Influenza virus is highly contagious that is, its entry into the human body in many cases leads to the development of the disease. The disease is accompanied by an increase in body temperature, and often the general condition improves in 3-5 days.*

Keywords: *symptoms and signs of the flu, forms of influenza, Causes of flu, Diagnosis and identification of influenza, Treatment of influenza and relief of illness, Complications of influenza, Prevention of influenza and application of preventive measures*

СИМПТОМЫ ГРИППА, ФОРМЫ, ПРИЧИНЫ, ДИАГНОСТИКА, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКА

Аннотация. *Грипп – острое инфекционное респираторное заболевание вирусной природы. Вирус гриппа обладает высокой контагиозностью, то есть его попадание в организм человека во многих случаях приводит к развитию заболевания. Заболевание сопровождается повышением температуры тела, нередко общее состояние улучшается через 3-5 дней.*

Ключевые слова: *симптомы и признаки гриппа, формы гриппа, Причины гриппа, Диагностика и выявление гриппа, Лечение гриппа и купирование заболевания, Осложнения гриппа, Профилактика гриппа и применение профилактических мер*

SYMPTOMS AND SIGNS OF THE FLU

- Influenza symptoms caused by intoxication:
- Very fast (for 3-4 hours) increase in signs of intoxication:
- An increase in body temperature — 39°C and higher;
- Strong tremors;
- Weakness;
- Pain in muscles and joints;
- Severe headache
- Watery eyes;
- Sensitivity to light.
- In parallel with intoxication, respiratory symptoms are observed:
- Sore throat;
- Dry cough;
- Runny nose.

Sometimes abdominal pain and diarrhea are observed. In flu, high body temperature can last for several days, and often does not decrease due to the effect of antipyretic drugs. If the disease is uncomplicated, the flu lasts 7-10 days. During this time, flu symptoms may gradually disappear, but general weakness may last up to two weeks.

Influenza is an acute infectious respiratory disease of a viral nature. Temperature indicator on the thermometer.

FORMS OF INFLUENCE

Influenza, like other acute respiratory viral infections, can have mild, moderate, severe and very severe forms. In addition, uncomplicated and complicated forms of the disease are distinguished.

CAUSES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF FLU

The causes of the disease are damage to the mucous membrane of the upper respiratory tract by influenza viruses. The source of infection (disease) is a person infected with influenza. The main route of transmission of the disease is airborne: coughing, sneezing, talking and even simple breathing. But the virus can be transmitted by household means - through handkerchiefs, food, sheets. The flu virus is highly contagious.

DIAGNOSING AND IDENTIFYING INFLUENZA

Diagnosis of influenza is usually based on clinical examination. In the event of a sudden increase in temperature, it is necessary to consult a doctor as soon as possible. A doctor's supervision is very important in the case of influenza, because it allows to determine the onset of possible bacterial complications in time. The appearance of complications is manifested by symptoms such as a re-increased temperature, increased cough and a worsening of the general condition after a slight improvement, and usually corresponds to 4-5 days of the disease. In this case, it is necessary to carry out additional tests - a general blood test, an X-ray of the chest and sinuses.

TREATMENT OF FLU AND RELIEF OF DISEASE

The treatment of influenza requires complex procedures, but the immune system plays a major role in fighting the flu and in the recovery of the body, and therefore it is necessary to take measures to stimulate the immune system. Full rest, drinking plenty of fluids (for detoxification), and limiting alcohol and smoking are recommended. At the same time, effective antiviral drugs significantly reduce the duration of the flu, fever and other symptoms. Other drugs used include:

1. Symptomatic medicinal drugs (antipyretic, expectorant);
2. Immunostimulants - such properties are especially abundant in vitamin C;
3. Interferon;
4. Antiviral drugs at different stages of the disease;
5. Antihistamines.

Antibiotics are prescribed only in the presence of secondary bacterial diseases, they are not effective against viruses at all, but it is often common among people to take antibiotics without a doctor's prescription when they have symptoms of a cold or flu.

Taking antibiotics against viruses is not only ineffective, but also increases the resistance of bacteria to antibiotics.

COMPLICATIONS OF FLU

Due to the fact that the influenza virus affects the epithelial cells of the respiratory tract, as a result of the complications of the disease, it is possible to cause bacterial diseases, including bronchitis, pneumonia, otitis, sinusitis or other sinus inflammations. Examples of serious bacterial complications are meningitis, inflammation of the cerebral cortex. Influenza can also aggravate existing chronic diseases in the patient.

PREVENTION OF INFLUENZA AND USE OF PROphylactic MEASURES

The most effective way to prevent the flu is to keep your immune system in good shape all year round. There are many ways to boost immunity, including:

Exercise the body;

Active lifestyle;

Proper and balanced nutrition;

The other main medical method is vaccination. Vaccination is given to a specific type (strain) of the virus 2-3 months before the beginning of the flu season (usually in October-November). Vaccination is more effective against more virus strains and more people. In this case, it allows to protect large social groups of the population. It is also recommended to use antiviral drugs as a preventive measure during epidemics. Observing hygiene rules, walking away from sick people, wearing special masks, paying attention to cleanliness when family members are sick, and frequent ventilation of the room will reduce the probability of getting sick.

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